

SURVEY ON NON-COMMUNICABLE DISEASES (NCDs).

Population living near public green spaces in Abidjan (Ages 16–65 years).

Name of interviewer

Date of interview

Time of interview

hh:mm

Mode of transportation

- Walking
- Bicycle
- Motorcycle
- Public transport
- Private car
- Others

Household number

Number of individuals in the household

Household GPS coordinates

latitude (x.y °)

longitude (x.y °)

altitude (m)

précision (m)

Housing status

- Owner
- Tenant

Type of housing

- Villa
- Ordinary house
- Row house
- Apartment
- Shared courtyard
- Mud hut
- Makeshift dwelling

Full name

Contact

Ethnic group

Sex

- Male
- Female

How old are you?

What is your level of education?

- No formal education
- Less than primary school
- Completed primary school
- Completed secondary school
- Completed high school or equivalent
- University
- Postgraduate degree
- Refused

Most recent professional activity

- Government employee
- Private sector employee
- Self-employed
- Volunteer
- Student
- Housewife / homemaker
- Retired
- Unemployed
- Disabled / unable to work
- Refused

What is your monthly income?

How would you describe your general health?

- Very good
- Good
- Poor
- Very poor

Have you consulted a doctor in the past 12 months?

- Yes
- No

What illness was diagnosed?

Do you smoke?

- Yes
- No

Do you smoke daily?

- Yes
- No

At what age did you start smoking daily?

Do you drink alcohol daily?

- Yes
- No

Frequency of alcohol consumption (past 12 months)

- Daily
- 5–6 days per week
- 1–4 days per week
- 1–3 days per month
- Less than once per month

Average number of drinks per day when you drink

Do you eat fruits?

- Yes
- No

How many fruits do you consume per week?

Do you eat sauces rich in vegetables?

- Yes
- No

How many times per week do you eat sauces rich in vegetables?

Which of these cardiovascular symptoms do you have?

- High blood pressure
- Shortness of breath when lying down
- Shortness of breath during effort
- Rapid breathing
- Frequent fatigue
- Swollen legs
- Palpitations
- Chest pain

Which of these bone disease symptoms do you have?

- Neck and back pain
- Back pain
- Neck and shoulder pain
- Elbow/wrist/hand pain
- Knee pain
- Joint pain
- Rheumatism

Which of these neurological symptoms do you have?

- Migraines
- Dizziness

Which of these mental signs do you have?

- Depression
- Fear
- Anxiety
- Panic
- Stress
- Talking to oneself

Which of these respiratory symptoms do you have?

- Upper respiratory infections
- Bronchitis, pneumonia
- Asthma
- Shortness of breath
- Wheezing
- Regular cough
- Fever
- Muscle aches
- Chest pain
- Headaches
- Frequent fatigue

Which of these digestive symptoms do you have?

- Intestinal pain
- Intestinal infections
- Chronic constipation
- Anal itching
- Blood in stool

Which of these skin disease symptoms do you have?

- Itching
- Red pimples

Which of these other symptoms do you have?

- Unexplained physical symptoms
- Acute urinary infections
- Diabetes
- Cancers